

Explore what *Investigating in Science* could look like to learn more about the Material World. (Table adapted from Fenton, 2011)

	Modelling	Classifying and Identifying	Pattern seeking	Making things or developing systems	Observing	Fair testing (scientific method)
This could be...	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Build a model atom and investigate the significance of electrons being on the outside...what is the connection to how electricity flows along a wire or how static electricity is created? <input type="checkbox"/> Create a story (words, role play, video animation, cartoons) that link familiar everyday concepts to explain physical changes of matter, eg, where does the water go when a puddle evaporates? <input type="checkbox"/> Make a model house using different materials to explore physical and chemical properties such as strength, waterproofing, or resistance to colour fading in direct sunlight. <input type="checkbox"/> Use a simulator and explore if it is a reasonable approximation to the real world. Try this lumps and powders dissolving simulator here. Click on red stopper to reset. <input type="checkbox"/> Record the time it takes for an ice cube of known size to melt completely. Test if a mathematical model that says a cube twice the size takes twice as long to melt a good fit with reality. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Collect samples of 10 different fibres or materials used to make clothing. Examine with a hand lens or magnifier. Can you classify these into different categories? On what basis did you make your decisions? <input type="checkbox"/> Observe a number of changes in the environment around you during the course of a day. How many are physical changes? How many chemical changes did you observe and what were they? <input type="checkbox"/> Survey the types of plastics you have at home. Do they have recycling codes, and can you use these to determine the most common type of plastic you have found? <input type="checkbox"/> Make your own acid-base indicators. Test different products used in cooking or cleaning from around the home. How many 'acids' or 'bases' did you find? How can you tell if they are strong acids or weak acids? <input type="checkbox"/> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Making careful observations of your pulse rate before you drink a cup of coffee or other caffeinated drink and again afterwards. Do certain chemicals in foods (eg, sugar based) or drinks affect your heart rate? <input type="checkbox"/> Have a look at the Periodic Table of the Elements. What patterns to you notice about the way the table is arranged? <input type="checkbox"/> Exploring the factors that help prevent iron rusting. Why is this important? Alternatively, when would you want to speed up the corrosion process? How could you do this? <input type="checkbox"/> Carry out a survey: Record which foods are high in salt or sugar. Do you see any patterns? What sort of foods do the students prefer to eat? Alternatively, can you link this to ideas in the Living World about healthy diets? <input type="checkbox"/> Do ice blocks containing sugar melt faster than ice that does not? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Make you own milk glue and test the strength of the glue you have made. Alternatively, is it waterproof? Can it withstand exposure to heat from the sun? How else could you test the suitability of your product? <input type="checkbox"/> Learn how to make plaster casts of animal tracks or make 'fossils' for your students to identify <input type="checkbox"/> Make a simple data logger for \$10. Use it to test for the amount of salt in an estuary or salt in foods. How will you calibrate this device? <input type="checkbox"/> Make a simple interactive animation, that explains how to use a piece of science equipment. <input type="checkbox"/> Research how other famous scientists made discoveries 'by luck' (serendipity) <input type="checkbox"/> Create a simple science game or simulator (Mac and PC). <input type="checkbox"/> Build simple play dough powered toys. How can you make them work most efficiently? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Over a period of time, record the changes that occur to an iron object left to rust outside. You might record images using a cell phone camera. What changes do you observe? <input type="checkbox"/> Using a transparent cup, record the stages of a teabag brewing as it is left in a hot cup of water. Record the way the tea leaf fluids spread out (diffuse) into the water. <input type="checkbox"/> Record the temperature as a block of Plaster of Paris dries (insert the thermometer into a straw so it can be removed easily). What do you notice? Does this signal a physical change has occurred or a chemical change? <input type="checkbox"/> Observe the species of insects or birds that come to feed on a plant that is very fragrant. From how far away can you detect the smell of the plant? Is there evidence that other animals have a better sense of smell than you? <input type="checkbox"/> Fill a shallow dish with milk and add one drop of food colouring to the centre. What do you observe? If you repeat with a fresh sample of milk, do you see the same pattern? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fair testing method <input type="checkbox"/> Deciding if a project is technology or science <input type="checkbox"/> DNA fingerprinting made simple – separating food colouring samples using 9 volt batteries. <input type="checkbox"/> Investigate the effect of sunlight on samples of rubber, ink, and paper. <input type="checkbox"/> Fair testing of different brands of paper towel to see which absorbs the most water <input type="checkbox"/> Which deodorants smell the most pleasant to boys compared to girls? <input type="checkbox"/> Investigate the best conditions for producing a long life battery using salty play dough. <input type="checkbox"/> Test what factors speed up a chemical reaction

Notes:

- The above are a few suggestions only. Please add to this document and save it for your own use on your home computer if you find it useful.
- Observations could be recorded digitally if appropriate; sounds, time lapse still images or motion video clips.
- Observational drawings are to be scientific observational drawings, with no shading. Dots and lines are allowed. The drawing must be done in pencil on A4 paper, with the specimen's name(s) printed in the lower left corner. It should be drawn directly from the observed object(s). A scale must be shown. (from [Taranaki Science Fair website](#))
- Investigations using animals must follow the guidelines outlined in this site [Caring for Animals](#) and the Animal Welfare Act 1999
- Investigations that involve practical work must follow health and safety guidelines as set out in this document ['Safety and Science Guidance Manual'](#)